

Decoding Options for the Symmetric and Asymmetric Turbo-Coded Two-Way Relay Channel

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Abstract—In this paper, we extend our recent work on joint decoding of trellis codes for the two-way relay channel to quaternary decoding of turbo codes and evaluate two approaches for rate adaptation. More specifically, we consider the uplink phase, which has been identified as the bottleneck, and apply a quaternary joint turbo decoder for both packets. For asymmetric channels, we evaluate two methods of adapting the code rate while keeping the standard LTE turbo codes. The first approach applies puncturing which is known in LTE as rate matching and adapts the codeword lengths while the second, less well-known, method reduces the message length and is known as expurgation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Two-Way Relay Channel (TWRC) represents the basic scenario for the application of new techniques to improve the communication efficiency in the network topologies which foresee the employment of a relay node, such as e.g. satellite communication and mobile intracell communication. The TWRC is composed by two users which communicate between themselves by the employment of a third entity. The communication process involves two separate phases, namely Multiple-access phase, from users to relay, and the Broadcast phase, from relay to users. Starting from this model, it is possible to easily extend new strategies and methods to larger and more complicated topologies. Many improvement applied to this scenario were proposed since Ahlswede et al. in [1] inspired the idea of Network Coding. This seminal work showed that for the broadcast phase of the TWRC only one transmission is needed to transmit the users' messages to each other, simply combining these messages into one instead of transmitting two messages. A substantial extension of network coding to the wireless scenario was given by Zhang and Liew et al. in [2], [3], which applied joint decoding to the concept of the signal superposition in the Multiple-access phase, creating Physical Layer Network Coding (PLNC). In [4], Katti et al. showed that this superimposition can be seen as an addition in the Galois field \mathbb{F}_2 for the binary case. Starting from this background, several solutions have been proposed to interpret the signal superposition in the multiple access phase by exploiting different decoding for the application of network coding. In [5], the authors proposed a strategy called *denoise-and-forward* in which the relay does not decode the joint message but only maps it into a discrete constellation before broadcasting

it. In [6], [7], Nazer and Gastpar introduced the *compute-and-forward method* where, thanks to the property of lattice codes and especially in Gaussian TWRC, the relay can decode linear functions of transmitted codewords. On the other hand, *soft demapping* is another, more general, alternative of the precedents because it allows the application of standard and off-the-shelf channel codes. Improvements to this approach can be found in [8], [9], where non-binary decoding is considered to decode standard LDPC codes or convolutional codes [10], [11]. Following this approach, we propose a non-binary decoding of LTE Turbo codes, highlighting the advantage of quaternary decoding, compared to binary decoding in terms of packet error rate for varying SNR. We focus our work mainly on the multiple access phase while keeping classic network coding in broadcast phase, since this represents the limit to the achievable rate on TWRC [12]. We show and compare several decoding options such as separate decoding, both for individual and combined packet, successive interference cancellation and joint decoding. We also test these decoding options in symmetric and asymmetric channel, adapting the rate by means to puncturing and expurgation.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider the two-way relay channel in which two users A and B exchange information packets \mathbf{u}_a , \mathbf{u}_b via a relay R and there is no direct link between the users. Such a setting typically occurs in satellite communications but also in cases of terrestrial relaying where only the relay has direct links to the users. We make use of the two-phase protocol, in which the packet exchange is performed in two steps,

- Multiple-access phase: Both users transmit their packets, \mathbf{u}_a and \mathbf{u}_b , to the relay.
- Broadcast phase: The relay retransmits the binary sum of both packets, $\mathbf{u}_{ab} \triangleq \mathbf{u}_a + \mathbf{u}_b$ to both users. Since both users know their own packet, they can obtain the other user's packet from the combined packet \mathbf{u}_{ab} .

This transmission scheme is illustrated in Fig. 1, where we can also see the close relationship to the other canonical example for network coding, the butterfly network. In wireless network coding, the relay can decode directly the combined packet \mathbf{u}_{ab} without having to recover the individual packets \mathbf{u}_a and \mathbf{u}_b .

Figure 1. Information exchange between users A and B over the two-way relay channel

In the following, we focus on the multiple-access phase, which can be identified as the bottleneck of the two-phase protocol and assume a flat fading channel,

$$y_n = h_{a,n}x_{a,n} + h_{b,n}x_{b,n} + w_n, \quad w_n \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1) \quad (1)$$

which includes the AWGN TWRC as a special case by setting $h_{a,n} = \sqrt{\text{SNR}_a}$, $h_{b,n} = \sqrt{\text{SNR}_b}$. For fast Rayleigh fading, the fading coefficients are i.i.d. with $h_{k,n} = |h_{k,n}^{(c)}|$, and $h_{k,n}^{(c)} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sqrt{\text{SNR}_k})$, $k \in \{a, b\}$.

Before transmission over the wireless channel, the message $\mathbf{u} = [u_1, \dots, u_K] \in \mathbb{F}_2^K$ is encoded into a codeword $\mathbf{c} = [c_1, \dots, c_N] \in \mathbb{F}_2^N$ by $\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{u}\mathbf{G}$, where $\mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{F}_2^{K \times N}$ denotes the generator matrix and the code rate is given by $R_c = \frac{K}{N}$. The coded bits $c_n \in \mathbb{F}_2$ are mapped to real or complex-valued QAM symbols x_n . In this paper, for ease of exposition, we restrict ourselves to BPSK with the mapping $x_n = \mu(c_n)$ such that $\mu(0) = -1$ and $\mu(1) = 1$. On the receiver side, we make use of soft decoding and apply a turbo decoder which expects log-likelihood ratio values (L-values) as input. For BPSK, the L-value corresponding to the coded bit c_n is given by

$$L_n = \ln \frac{P[c_n = 1 | y_n]}{P[c_n = 0 | y_n]} = 4h_n y_n. \quad (2)$$

A. Rate Matching by Puncturing

The most common method for adapting the code rate while keeping the same encoder and decoder is given by *puncturing*, also known as *rate matching* in the context of LTE. With puncturing, only a fraction of the code bits is transmitted while at the receiver, these missing bits are replaced by zero L-values before decoding. For all simulations in this paper, we have used the 3GPP turbo code of message length $K = 40$ bits and a mother code rate of $R_{c,m} = \frac{10}{33}$ and puncturing according to Table I. Fig. 2 shows the simulated packet error rates (PER) with these code rates and BPSK over the AWGN channel.

Table I
SELECTED WORD LENGTHS AND CODE RATES OF 3GPP TURBO CODE

R_c	$\frac{10}{33}$	$\frac{1}{3}$	$\frac{2}{5}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{2}{3}$	$\frac{4}{5}$
N	132	120	100	80	60	50

Figure 2. Packet error rates with 3GPP turbo codes with message length $K = 40$ over the BI-AWGN channel.

III. DECODING METHODS AT THE RELAY

In this section, we present various methods for obtaining the desired packet combination \mathbf{u}_{ab} at the relay, starting from the simplest approach.

A. Separate Decoding

1) *Decoding for Individual Packets \mathbf{u}_a and \mathbf{u}_b* : The obvious decoding method at the relay is to first decode both packets, before transmitting the combination of both in the broadcasting phase. The L-value for a coded bit of user A is defined as $L_a \triangleq \ln \frac{P[c_a=1|y]}{P[c_a=0|y]}$, where we skipped the time index n for notational brevity. For the simultaneous transmission of both users' packets, we obtain with (1) and for BPSK mapping

$$\begin{aligned} L_a &= \ln \frac{P[c_a = 1, c_b = 0 | y] + P[c_a = 1, c_b = 0 | y]}{P[c_a = 1, c_b = 0 | y] + P[c_a = 1, c_b = 0 | y]} \\ &= \ln \frac{p(y | x_a = 1, x_b = -1) + p(y | x_a = 1, x_b = 1)}{p(y | x_a = -1, x_b = -1) + p(y | x_a = -1, x_b = 1)} \\ &= \ln \frac{\exp(h^-(2y - h^-)) + \exp(h^+(2y - h^+))}{\exp(-h^-(2y + h^-)) + \exp(-h^+(2y + h^+))} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $h^- \triangleq h_a - h_b$, $h^+ \triangleq h_a + h_b$ and in the same way for \mathbf{u}_b ,

$$L_b = \ln \frac{\exp(-h^-(2y + h^-)) + \exp(h^+(2y - h^+))}{\exp(-h^+(2y + h^+)) + \exp(h^-(2y + h^-))} \quad (4)$$

These L-values are computed for all coded bits of a codeword and are then fed into the decoder.

2) *Decoding for the Combined (XORed) Packet \mathbf{u}_{ab}* : Instead of decoding first the packets \mathbf{u}_a and \mathbf{u}_b , the relay can exploit the linearity of the code and decode directly for the combined codeword $\mathbf{u}_{ab} = \mathbf{u}_a + \mathbf{u}_b$ ¹. Since $\mathbf{c}_{ab} \triangleq \mathbf{c}_a + \mathbf{c}_b = \mathbf{u}_a\mathbf{G} + \mathbf{u}_b\mathbf{G} = (\mathbf{u}_a + \mathbf{u}_b)\mathbf{G}$ is also a codeword of the same

¹Addition on bits or bit vectors is defined as the addition in the Galois field \mathbb{F}_2 , which is the same the XOR operation.

code, we can use the same decoder with the corresponding L-values

$$\begin{aligned} L_{ab} &\triangleq \ln \frac{P[c_{ab} = 1 | y]}{P[c_{ab} = 0 | y]} \\ &= 4h_a h_b + \ln \frac{\cosh(2h^- y)}{\cosh(2h^+ y)} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

B. Successive Interference Cancellation (SIC)

A straightforward improvement of separate decoding is possible by successive interference cancellation (SIC): After the successful decoding of one user's packet, say \mathbf{u}_a , the corresponding transmit signal \mathbf{x}_a is reconstructed and, after multiplication with the fading coefficient h_a , is subtracted from the received signal \mathbf{y} . Error propagation can be avoided by an additional error detection code, e.g. CRC (cyclic redundancy check).

C. Joint Decoding

The packets of both users can be decoded jointly by considering the joint message, such that

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_a \\ \hat{\mathbf{u}}_b \end{bmatrix} = \max_{\mathbf{u}_a, \mathbf{u}_b} \{p(\mathbf{y} | \mathbf{u}_a, \mathbf{u}_b)\} \quad (6)$$

This joint message is related to the joint codeword in the same way as the two single codewords,

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{c}_a \\ \mathbf{c}_b \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_a \\ \mathbf{u}_b \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{G} \quad (7)$$

Decoding for the joint message $\begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_a \\ \hat{\mathbf{u}}_b \end{bmatrix}$ can be performed by a straightforward extension of the standard binary turbo decoder which is based on BCJR component decoders. To this end, a new trellis representation for quaternary message and code symbols has to be defined [10], and the decoder input is now given by quaternary L-values,

$$\mathbf{L} \triangleq \ln \begin{bmatrix} P[c_a = 0, c_b = 0 | y] \\ P[c_a = 0, c_b = 1 | y] \\ P[c_a = 1, c_b = 0 | y] \\ P[c_a = 1, c_b = 1 | y] \end{bmatrix} = - \begin{bmatrix} (y + h_a + h_b)^2 \\ (y + h_a - h_b)^2 \\ (y - h_a + h_b)^2 \\ (y - h_a - h_b)^2 \end{bmatrix}.$$

IV. RATE ADAPTATION

For all simulations we assume without loss of generality $\text{SNR}_a \geq \text{SNR}_b$ and we study two possibilities for adapting the code rates such that $R_a \geq R_b$, namely *puncturing* and *expurgation*.

A. Puncturing

Puncturing is the usual approach to adapt the code rate while keeping the same encoder/decoder pair. From a given mother code, higher code rates are obtained by transmitting only a part of the coded bits, while the message length K is constant. Denoting by N the length of the mother codeword, he have

$$R_a = \frac{K}{N_a} \geq R_b = \frac{K}{N_b} \Rightarrow N_a \leq N_b = N$$

For the computation of the L-values which correspond to punctured bits of user A, we simply set $h_a = 0$.

It has to be noted that while puncturing is a simple and efficient method for adapting the code rate, it has little effect when used for the TWRC since the duration of the multiple-access phase is determined by the unpunctured codeword and hence the increase of R_a does not translate in a higher overall rate. The only benefit of puncturing in this case is the reduction of the transmit power.

B. Expurgation

While puncturing reduces the codeword length N to adapt the code rate, expurgation reduces the message length K . In order to keep the same encoder and decoder, the expurgated message bits are replaced by fixed values. Therefore, for $\text{SNR}_a \geq \text{SNR}_b$, we have to reduce the message length of user B, i.e. $K_b \leq K_a = K$ and $N_a = N_b = N$. In this paper, no effort was made to find the optimum bit positions for expurgation and the first $K - K_b$ message bits of user B have been set to zero, $u_{b,1} = \dots = u_{b,K-K_b} = 0$.

The L-values which correspond to expurgated bits u_b are then given by (the mapping from message bits to coded bits is trivial for systematic encoders like for the 3GPP turbo code)

$$L_a = L_{ab} = 4h_a (y + h_b), \quad L_b = -\infty$$

and for the quaternary decoder

$$\mathbf{L} = - \begin{bmatrix} (y + h_a + h_b)^2 \\ -\infty \\ (y - h_a + h_b)^2 \\ -\infty \end{bmatrix}$$

Naturally, if all bits of user B are expurgated, we obtain a single-user problem and the quaternary decoder becomes binary.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

A. Symmetric Channel

Fig. 3 shows simulated PERs for a symmetric AWGN and a symmetric fast Rayleigh fading channel. For all cases, the 3GPP turbo code with $K = 40$, $N = 132$ has been applied and the performance over the single-user channel is shown as reference. The best results for the multiple-access phase of the TWRC (AWGN or fast fading) are obtained by *joint decoding*. For the AWGN TWRC, it is not possible to recover the individual messages \mathbf{u}_a , \mathbf{u}_b at the relay whereas for the fast fading TWRC the individual messages are obtained with (nearly) the same error rate as the combined message \mathbf{u}_{ab} . Binary decoding for the combined message is a valid option although it loses 0.5 dB for AWGN and 2.5 dB for fading compared to joint quaternary decoding.

Figure 3. Packet error rates for the symmetric TWRC

B. Asymmetric Channel and Rate Adaptation by Puncturing

In Fig. 4 we can observe the PERs for an asymmetric fast fading channel with SNR differences of 3 dB, 6 dB and 10 dB. For all decoding approaches, the performance is unavoidably dominated by the worse channel. An interesting results is that SIC and joint decoding perform almost equally, which gives preference to SIC for its lower complexity, provided that error detection is in place. This can be included at low complexity by an additional CRC code and should be considered in a more complete evaluation. Another interesting outcome is that the performance gap between quaternary (joint) and binary (separate) decoding reduces for strong SNR imbalance.

Figure 4. PERs for asymmetric TWRC

While puncturing cannot increase the data rate for the user with the strong channel, it reduces its transmit power. In Fig. 5,

the PER for SIC is shown for an SNR gap of 10 dB and various codeword length which have been obtained by puncturing of the (132, 40) mother code. While for modest puncturing to code rates up to 1/2 ($N_a = 2K = 80$), there is hardly any performance difference, for higher code rates (i.e. $N_a \leq 60$), the PER increases significantly.

Figure 5. PERs for asymmetric TWRC with $\Delta\text{SNR} = 10$ dB and SIC decoding.

C. Asymmetric Channel and Rate Adaptation by Puncturing

While with puncturing we cannot adapt the bit rate of a single user, this is possible by expurgation since by varying the message length K , the number of bits per multiple-access phase can be different for each user. We simulated various message lengths for an SNR gap of 10 dB, as shown in Fig. 6. We can observe that, in principle, this approach allows to transmit with different bit rates in the multiple-access phase while using the encoder/decoder of the mother code.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper we proved the benefits of joint quaternary decoding applied to off-the-shelf LTE turbo channel codes in the TWRC, especially in case of a symmetric channel. Joint decoding exhibits better error performance compared to separate decoding and SIC, approaching single user performance for symmetric channel conditions. This comes at the expenses of a computational complexity increase, which does not pay-off for asymmetric channels conditions. For the asymmetric channel, quaternary decoding and SIC have very similar performance. Performance differences depends on the rate adaptation adaptation (puncturing or expurgation) strategy and relative difference between channel qualities. We shall remark that there is room for improvement by optimizing the expurgation strategy. This can be easily done for LDPC by exploiting the code Tanner graph for the selection of expurgated bit positions.

Figure 6. PERs with code expurgation

Further investigation of joint decoding strategies for the asymmetric channel appeared relevant. Also the extension to time sharing schemes and multiuser scenarios is identified as future work.

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